

Mobile Cloud Middleware: A New Service for Mobile Users

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Abstract : Cloud Computing (CC) and Mobile Cloud Computing (MCC) have advanced rapidly the last few years. Today, MCC undergoes fast improvement and progress in terms of hardware (memory, embedded sensors, power consumption, touch screen, etc.) software (more and more sophisticated mobile applications) and transmission (higher data transmission rates achieved with different technologies such as 3Gs). This paper presents a review on the concept of CC and MCC. Then, it discusses what has been done regarding middleware in CC and MCC. Later, it shows the architecture of our proposed middleware along with its functionalities which will be provided to mobile clients in order to overcome the well-known problems (such as low battery power, slow CPU speed and, little memory etc.).

Keywords : context-aware, cloud computing, middleware, mobile cloud computing

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